

MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF FUNCTIONALIZED GRAPHENE/ETHYLENE VINYL ACETATE NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The discovery of graphene in 2004 has added a new dimension in the field of materials science research. Recently, the use of graphene as nanofiller in the preparation of polymer nanocomposites has attracted a great deal of interest due to its excellent electrical conductivity, low co-efficient of thermal expansion (CTE), high aspect ratio, easy to synthesis and surface modification, etc [1]. Graphene based polymer nanocomposites exhibit improved mechanical, thermal, electrical conductivity and gas barrier properties [1,2]. However, a pristine graphene material does not disperse well in the polymer matrix due to the compatibility problem. In order to overcome this shortcoming surface modification of graphene is very essential. Ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) copolymer has been selected as a matrix polymer in the present study.

2 Experimental

2.1 Preparation of surface modified graphene and EVA nanocomposites

Graphite oxide was prepared by modified Hummers method [3]. For surface modification, 3 g of octadecyl amine (ODA) in 100 ml hot ethanol was added to the graphite oxide dispersion in water. The mixture was refluxed at 100°C for 24 h. Then 10 ml of hydrazine monohydrate was added followed by refluxing at 100°C for 24 h.

For nanocomposites preparation, desired amount of octadecyl amine modified graphene (ODA-G) dispersion was added to the EVA solution in toluene and refluxed for 20 hour. Finally benzoyl peroxide was added and the solution casted material was dried in vacuum oven for 24 hour and compression molded at 150°C.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 XPS analysis

Fig. 1 shows the C1s XPS spectra of ODA-G. Five different types of carbon with different chemical environments were observed in ODA-G. The C1s peak of nonoxygenated ring C; the C in the C-O bonds; the carbonyl C; the carboxylate carbon (O-C=O) and epoxy carbon were present [4]. These five types of carbon were present in the graphite oxide. However, the peak intensity and position were changed in the ODA-G.

Fig. 1. C1s XPS of ODA-G

3.2 TEM analysis

Fig. 2 shows the TEM image of the EVA-28/ODA-G composite with a ODA-G content of 3 wt.%. It showed that the graphene sheets were dispersed homogeneously in the EVA-28 matrix. The good dispersion of graphene sheets should be due to the good interfacial interaction between the modified graphene and polymer matrix. The TEM image also shows the presence of a few layers of graphene in the composite.

Fig. 2. TEM image of EVA-28/ODA-G (3 wt.%) nanocomposites

3.3 DMA analysis

Fig. 3 shows the storage modulus of pure EVA-28 and its nanocomposites with ODA-G. The mobility of the polymer chains is restricted in presence of graphene resulting the enhancement of storage modulus in the nanocomposites. It has also been found that the glass transition temperature of the nanocomposites is increased and the height of the $\tan \delta$ peak is decreased. This indicates that the heat buildup is less in case of the nanocomposites.

Fig. 3. Storage modulus vs. temperature of EVA-28 and nanocomposite (inset: $\tan \delta$ vs. temperature).

3.4 TG analysis

Fig. 4 shows that the weight loss for the first step in the nanocomposites is relatively higher and may be attributed due to the degradation of alkyl chains present in ODA-G. However, the final step degradation temperature of the nanocomposite is much higher in comparison to neat EVA-28 which is possibly due to the barrier effect of the

homogeneously dispersed graphene, which inhibit the cooperative motion of small molecules during decomposition.

Fig. 4. TG profile of pure EVA and nanocomposite

4. Conclusion

The nanocomposites of EVA with ODA-G have been prepared successfully by solution mixing techniques and it shows improved mechanical and thermal properties.

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